

Panagia Parigoritissa, Arta

also known as “Virgin Mary of Consolation”

By Marina Toumpouri, Centre for Medieval Arts and Rituals, University of Cyprus

Entry tags: Christian, Greece, Religious Group, Christian Orthodox, Religious Place, Epirus, Orthodoxy

The church of Panagia Parigoritissa (meaning Virgin Mary of Consolation) at the centre of the city of Arta, Epirus, is dedicated to the Annunciation. It was constructed around the end of the 13th century by the despot of Epirus Nikephoros I Komnenos Doukas, his wife Anna Palaiologina and their son Thomas, as indicated by the inscription on the western wall (Κομνηνοδούκας δεσπότης Νικηφόρος Άννα βασιλί[ισσα] κομνη[οδοούκαινα] Κομνηνόβλαστος δεσπότης Θωμάς μέγας Κομνην[οί] Ελλάδος α[υτάνακτες] ή Κομνην[ών] κ[λάδος] αγγελωνύμων). The church was formerly the katholikon (main church) of a Monastery, of which currently the Refectory and the monks' or nuns' cells are still preserved. The three-storey katholikon was built following an original model, not encountered elsewhere, in particular the way the dome is supported, resting on eight pilasters that support three rows of columns. The whole space under the dome is therefore remaining undisturbed. The church's ground floor has an octagonal plan, while the first floor is of the cross-in-square type. It possesses two chapels (north and south) dedicated to the Taxiarchs (Archangels) and Saint John the Baptist, which communicate with the narthex. In the east the church ends in five apses. The church has a square, block-like exterior. On its horizontal roofline appear five domes and a lantern. The interior is decorated with brickwork, carved elements, blind arcades, in some cases polychrome. The base of the dome is also adorned with sculptural decoration, carved by craftsmen from the West, possibly Italy. The main dome features mosaic depictions of the Pantocrator, the Prophets, cherubim and seraphim that are contemporary with the monument. They were most probably executed by two different teams of craftsmen, believed to have come from either the byzantine capital, Constantinople, or, Thessaloniki. The wall-paintings in the sanctuary are the work of monk Ananias and date from 1558. Those in the nave were probably executed in the late 17th or early 18th century, while the paintings in the narthex are even later. The church originally had marble revetment, up to the level of the surrounding galleries, a few fragments of which are still remaining above the main entrance on the west side. The built iconostasis replaced the original one made of marble, of which only some pieces are still preserved. The church of Parigoritissa was built on the site of an earlier, smaller church, parts of which are visible on the north side of the nave. Outside the south west corner of the church are still preserved the ruins of a smaller, also earlier church, possibly of the 12th century. The cross-in-square church with three apses at the east, was likely used as funeral chapel, after Parigoritissa (the katholikon) was built. The Monastery is mentioned for the first time as a convent for nuns in a sigillium (decree) of 1578 by Patriarch Ieremias II. To the south-east of the katholikon is found a rectangular, barrel-vaulted building, which was the Refectory of the Monastery. It currently houses an exhibition of sculptures from the early Christian period to the 14th century that originate from byzantine monuments in Arta and its vicinity.

Date Range: 1290 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Panagia Parigoritissa

Region tags: Greece

Church of Panagia Parigoritissa at the centre of the city of Arta in Epirus, Greece.

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Other [specify]: No, yet it is found currently in the very centre of the city of Arta.

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

↳ A single structure

– Yes

↳ The structure has a definite shape

– Square

Notes: The church has a square blocklike exterior.

↳ One single feature

– Other [specify]: The church is in the middle of the city of Arta so there was planning for accessing it and for ameliorating the surrounding areas.

↳ A group of structures:

– No

Notes: The church is a single structure. Yet, next to it can be found the monk's cells, and the Refectory.

↳ A group of features:

– No

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– Yes

Notes: The church was the katholikon of a Moanstery that no longer exists.

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Worship

↳ Worship:

– Communal

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– Yes

Notes: The wall-paintings in the sanctuary are the work of monk Ananias and date from 1558. Those in the nave were probably executed in the late 17th or early 18th century, while the paintings in the narthex are even later. The church originally had marble revetments.

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– No

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:

– No

Notes: The church is is dedicated to the Annunciation.

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

– No

Notes: The church is is dedicated to the Annunciation.

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1: Orlandos, A. *H Parigoritissa Tis Artis*. Athens: The Archeological Society of Athens, 1963.

– Source 2: Ministry of Culture of Greece. *Church of the Parigoritissa at Arta*. Athens, 2014.

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– Yes

↳ Type of feature

– Plantings

– Other [specify]: The monument is in the middle of the modern city of Arta, so many features are associated to it.

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– No

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: http://www.religiousgreece.gr/epirus-thessaly/-/asset_publisher/bD2layf9w5H8/content/i-n-panagias-paregoretisses

– Source 1 Description: Virtual tour of Panagia Parigoritissa

– Source 2 URL: <https://www.thebyzantinelegacy.com/parigoritissa>

– Source 2 Description: Panagia Parigoritissa, Byzantine legacy entry

– Source 3 URL: <https://efaart.gr/portfolio/panagia-parigoritisa/>

– Source 3 Description: Panagia Parigoritissa, Ephorate of Antiquities of Arta

– Source 1 URL:

http://www.tap.gr/tapadb/components/com_jshopping/files/demo_products/144_Parigoritissa_Artas.pdf

– Source 1 Description: Ministry of Culture of Greece. Church of the Parigoritissa at Arta. Athens, n.d.

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– No

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– Yes

↳ Type of excavation:

– Scientific

Notes: The excavations were undertaken by the Ephorate of Antiquities of Arta.

↳ Years of excavation:

–Year range: 1960's

Name of excavation

–Official or descriptive name: There is not an official name

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– Yes

Is there a distinct boundary between the place and the urban fabric:

– No

Is the place located significantly within the urban fabric:

Is the place centrally located, or at the crossroads of significant pathways?

– Yes

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– No

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– Yes

Specify

–King or emperor

Notes: The church was built by the despot of Epirus Nikephoros I Komnenos Doukas, his wife Anna Palaiologina and their son Thomas.

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– No

Notes: Yet, specific groups of craftsmen worked for the church's completion.

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– No

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– No

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– Yes

Is this sponsor of the same religious group/tradition as the main usage of the place:

– Yes

Notes: The church was built by the despot of Epirus Nikephoros I Komnenos Doukas, his wife Anna Palaiologina and their son Thomas.

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Other [specify]: The church was the katholikon (main church) of a monastery, so none of the above reasons has motivated its construction.

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

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Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– Yes

Type of excavation:

– Scientific

Notes: The excavations were undertaken by the Ephorate of Antiquities of Arta.

Years of excavation:

– Year range: 1960's

Name of excavation

– Official or descriptive name: There is not an official name

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Other [specify]: No, yet it is found currently in the very centre of the city of Arta.

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– Yes

Type of feature

– Plantings

– Other [specify]: The monument is in the middle of the modern city of Arta, so many features are associated to it.

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– Yes

Is there a distinct boundary between the place and the urban fabric:

– No

- ↳ Is the place located significantly within the urban fabric:
Is the place centrally located, or at the crossroads of significant pathways?
– Yes

Is the place situated in a rural setting:
– No

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:
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Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

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– Yes

- ↳ The structure has a definite shape
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Notes: The church has a square blocklike exterior.

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– Other [specify]: The church is in the middle of the city of Arta so there was planning for accessing it and for ameliorating the surrounding areas.

- ↳ A group of structures:
– No

Notes: The church is a single structure. Yet, next to it can be found the monk's cells, and the Refectory.

- ↳ A group of features:
– No

- ↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:
– Yes

Notes: The church was the katholikon of a Moastery that no longer exists.

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

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↳ Worship:

– Communal

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– Yes

Notes: The wall-paintings in the sanctuary are the work of monk Ananias and date from 1558. Those in the nave were probably executed in the late 17th or early 18th century, while the paintings in the narthex are even later. The church originally had marble revetments.

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– No

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– No

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:

– No

Notes: The church is is dedicated to the Annunciation.

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

– No

Notes: The church is dedicated to the Annunciation.

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– No

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– Yes

↳ Specify

– King or emperor

Notes: The church was built by the despot of Epirus Nikephoros I Komnenos Doukas, his wife Anna Palaiologina and their son Thomas.

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Notes: Yet, specific groups of craftsmen worked for the church's completion.

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Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

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Was the place created as the result of an event:

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Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

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↳ Is this sponsor of the same religious group/tradition as the main usage of the place:

– Yes

Notes: The church was built by the despot of Epirus Nikephoros I Komnenos Doukas, his wife Anna Palaiologina and their son Thomas.

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Other [specify]: The church was the katholikon (main church) of a monastery, so none of the above reasons has motivated its construction.

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Design and Material Remains

Is decoration present:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):

– Yes

↳ On the outside:

– No

↳ On the inside:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– Yes

Notes: The decoration of the monument is both part of the church (sculpture, brickwork), as well as attached to the building (icons, wooden furniture).

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– Yes

↳ Are there gods depicted:

– Yes

Notes: Christ, the Son of God, is depicted at the dome.

↳ Are there other supernatural beings depicted:

– Yes

Notes: Angels, Cherubim and Seraphim.

↳ Are there humans depicted:

– Yes

Notes: Saints, the Mother of God.

↳ Are there animals depicted:

– Yes

Notes: The sculptural decoration of the church includes animals.

↳ Are there animal-human hybrids depicted:

– No

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– No

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– No

↳ Are there statues present:

– No

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– Yes

↳ Reliefs representing the god(s) worshipped at the place:

– No

↳ Reliefs representing mythological narratives:

– No

↳ Reliefs representing human/historical narratives:

– Yes

Notes: The Nativity of Christ.

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: Decorative vegetal motifs are also present.

↳ Are there paintings present:

– Yes

↳ Are they panel paintings [movable]:

– Yes

Notes: Icons.

↳ Are they wall paintings:

– Yes

↳ Type

– 'True' fresco

– Secco

↳ Paintings representing the gods worshipped at the place:

– Yes

Notes: Christ, the Mother of God, Saints, Angels.

↳ Paintings representing mythological narratives:

– No

↳ Paintings representing human/historical narratives:

– Yes

Notes: Scenes from the life of Christ and Saints.

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: The paintings do not belong to the original decoration of the monument, so they were adjusted to the existing iconographic subjects.

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– Yes

↳ Mosaics representing the god(s) worshipped at the place:

– Yes

Notes: Christ Pantokrator is depicted on the dome.

↳ Mosaics representing mythological narratives:

– No

↳ Mosaics representing human/historical narratives:

– No

↳ Abstract mosaics:

– No

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: Cherubims and Seraphims are also depicted.

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– Yes

↳ Are the inscriptions ornamental:

– No

↳ Are the inscriptions informative/declarative
[e.g. historical narratives, calendars, donor lists etc...]

– Yes

Notes: The inscriptions as is always the case in Christian Orthodox churches provide information regarding the person/Saint and the event depicted. On the western wall can be found also the dedicatory inscription referring to the foundation of the church.

↳ Are the inscription a formal dedication:

– No

Notes: Yet, on the western wall can be found also the dedicatory inscription referring to the foundation of the church.

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: On the western wall can be found also the dedicatory inscription referring to the foundation of the church.

↳ Other type of decoration:

– Yes [specify]: The church had originally marble revetment.

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– No

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not)

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic)

– Yes

Notes: Angels, Seraphim and Cherubim.

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract)

– No

↳ Portrayals of afterlife

– No

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols)

– Yes

Notes: Crosses, the Son of God.

↳ Humans

– Yes

↳ Supernatural narratives

– No

↳ Human narratives

– Yes

Notes: Scenes from the Life of Christ and Saints.

↳ Other [Specify]

– Other [specify]: The iconographic programme (mosaics and wall paintings) was executed in different phases, so it is not a complete and planned one as is the case in monuments planned and painted in a single phase.

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– No

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Earth

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Sand

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Clay

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Plaster

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Wood

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Grass

– I don't know

↳ Stone

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: Pigments and binders used for the frescoes.

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– No

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– No

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– No

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Earth

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↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Sand

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

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↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

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↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: Pigments and binders used for the frescoes.

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– No

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):

– Yes

↳ On the outside:

– No

↳ On the inside:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– Yes

Notes: The decoration of the monument is both part of the church (sculpture, brickwork), as well as attached to the building (icons, wooden furniture).

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– Yes

↳ Are there gods depicted:

– Yes

Notes: Christ, the Son of God, is depicted at the dome.

↳ Are there other supernatural beings depicted:

– Yes

Notes: Angels, Cherubim and Seraphim.

↳ Are there humans depicted:

– Yes

Notes: Saints, the Mother of God.

↳ Are there animals depicted:

– Yes

Notes: The sculptural decoration of the church includes animals.

↳ Are there animal-human hybrids depicted:

– No

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– No

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– No

↳ Are there statues present:

– No

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– Yes

↳ Reliefs representing the god(s) worshipped at the place:

– No

↳ Reliefs representing mythological narratives:

– No

↳ Reliefs representing human/historical narratives:

– Yes

Notes: The Nativity of Christ.

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: Decorative vegetal motifs are also present.

↳ Are there paintings present:

– Yes

↳ Are they panel paintings [movable]:

– Yes

Notes: Icons.

↳ Are they wall paintings:

– Yes

↳ Type

– 'True' fresco

– Secco

↳ Paintings representing the gods worshipped at the place:

– Yes

Notes: Christ, the Mother of God, Saints, Angels.

↳ Paintings representing mythological narratives:

– No

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– Yes

Notes: Scenes from the life of Christ and Saints.

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: The paintings do not belong to the original decoration of the monument, so they were adjusted to the existing iconographic subjects.

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– Yes

↳ Mosaics representing the god(s) worshipped at the place:

– Yes

Notes: Christ Pantokrator is depicted on the dome.

↳ Mosaics representing mythological narratives:

– No

↳ Mosaics representing human/historical narratives:

– No

↳ Abstract mosaics:

– No

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: Cherubims and Seraphims are also depicted.

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– Yes

↳ Are the inscriptions ornamental:

– No

↳ Are the inscriptions informative/declarative
[e.g. historical narratives, calendars, donor lists etc...]

– Yes

Notes: The inscriptions as is always the case in Christian Orthodox churches provide

information regarding the person/Saint and the event depicted. On the western wall can be found also the dedicatory inscription referring to the foundation of the church.

↳ Are the inscription a formal dedication:

– No

Notes: Yet, on the western wall can be found also the dedicatory inscription referring to the foundation of the church.

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: On the western wall can be found also the dedicatory inscription referring to the foundation of the church.

↳ Other type of decoration:

– Yes [specify]: The church had originally marble revetment.

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not)

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic)

– Yes

Notes: Angels, Seraphim and Cherubim.

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract)

– No

↳ Portrayals of afterlife

– No

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols)

– Yes

Notes: Crosses, the Son of God.

↳ Humans

– Yes

↳ Supernatural narratives

– No

↳ Human narratives

– Yes

Notes: Scenes from the Life of Christ and Saints.

↳ Other [Specify]

– Other [specify]: The iconographic programme (mosaics and wall paintings) was executed in different phases, so it is not a complete and planned one as is the case in monuments planned and painted in a single phase.

Beliefs and Practices

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– No

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

↳ How strict is pilgrimage:

– optional (common)

Notes: Pilgrims and also tourists and people interested in archaeology, history and architecture visit the monument.

↳ Are pilgrimages the main reason for construction/establishment of the place:

– No

↳ Are pilgrimages to this place associated with significant life events:

– No

↳ Does pilgrimage to this place involve following established routes (roads):

– No

Is divination present:

– No

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– No

Notes: Outside the south west corner of the church are still preserved the ruins of a smaller church. It was likely used as funeral chapel, after Parigoritissa was built.

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:

– No

Notes: The largest ritual taking place is on the day of the commemoration of the Annunciation, the feast day of the church.

↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

Notes: Services and other Christian Orthodox sacred Mysteries (Sacraments).

↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:

–specify: Unknown

↳ How often do these rituals take place:

–specify: If not every day then at least once a week, each Sunday.

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

– Yes

Notes: The services and every liturgy taking place is following strictly the Christian Orthodox rite.

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

– Yes

Notes: The services and every liturgy taking place is following strictly the Christian Orthodox rite.

↳ Are there synchronic practices:

– No

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:

– No

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– No

Is a supreme high god is present:

– No

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– No

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– No

Notes: Yet, on the 25th of March on the day of the commemoration of the Annunciation is the feast of the church.

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– No

Are previously human spirits present:

– No

Are festivals present:

– No

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– No

Notes: Yet, pilgrims may offer whatever they wish such as olive oil, bread, wine, ex-votos or even monetary or other offerings.

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– No

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Notes: Yet, outside the south west corner of the church are still preserved the ruins of a smaller church. It was likely used as funerary chapel, after Parigoritissa was built.

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– No

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Yes

Is it required:

– Yes

Is there cleansing (for the maintenance):

– No

Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:

– Yes

↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff:

– Yes

Notes: The maintenance is performed by specialists such as archaeologists, architects, engineers etc.

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: The church being a historical monument, the aim is that it is preserved and maintained for future generations.

Are formal burials present:

– No

Notes: Yet, the smaller church in ruins must have been used as a funerary chapel, so there must have been burials around the main church.

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Notes: Yet, humans may pray to God at this space. Also, the divine liturgy is taking place there.

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– No

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Notes: Yet, humans can pray to the Virgin and the Saints there.

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– No

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– No

Notes: Outside the south west corner of the church are still preserved the ruins of a smaller church. It was likely used as funeral chapel, after Parigoritissa was built.

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Notes: Yet, outside the south west corner of the church are still preserved the ruins of a smaller church. It was likely used as funerary chapel, after Parigoritissa was built.

Are formal burials present:

– No

Notes: Yet, the smaller church in ruins must have been used as a funerary chapel, so there must have been burials around the main church.

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– No

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are previously human spirits present:

– No

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– No

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Notes: Yet, humans may pray to God at this space. Also, the divine liturgy is taking place there.

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– No

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Notes: Yet, humans can pray to the Virgin and the Saints there.

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– No

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– No

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– No

Ritual and Performance

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:

– No

Notes: The largest ritual taking place is on the day of the commemoration of the Annunciation, the feast day of the church.

↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

Notes: Services and other Christian Orthodox sacred Mysteries (Sacraments).

↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:

– specify: Unknown

↳ How often do these rituals take place:

– specify: If not every day then at least once a week, each Sunday.

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

– Yes

Notes: The services and every liturgy taking place is following strictly the Christian Orthodox rite.

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

– Yes

Notes: The services and every liturgy taking place is following strictly the Christian Orthodox rite.

↳ Are there synchronic practices:

– No

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:

– No

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– No

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– No

Notes: Yet, pilgrims may offer whatever they wish such as olive oil, bread, wine, ex-votos or even monetary or other offerings.

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– No

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Yes

↳ Is it required:

– Yes

↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance):

– No

↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:

– Yes

↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff:

– Yes

Notes: The maintenance is performed by specialists such as archaeologists, architects, engineers etc.

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: The church being a historical monument, the aim is that it is preserved and maintained for future generations.

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

↳ How strict is pilgrimage:

– optional (common)

Notes: Pilgrims and also tourists and people interested in archaeology, history and architecture visit the monument.

↳ Are pilgrimages the main reason for construction/establishment of the place:

– No

↳ Are pilgrimages to this place associated with significant life events:

– No

↳ Does pilgrimage to this place involve following established routes (roads):

– No

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– No

Notes: Yet, on the 25th of March on the day of the commemoration of the Annunciation is the feast of the church.

Are festivals present:

– No

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– No

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– No

Institutions and Scriptures

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– No

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– No

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– No

Notes: Yet, the monument still functions as a church.

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– No

Notes: The Refectory of the Monastery is currently used as a museum.

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– No

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– No

Notes: There are monastic cells still preserved next to the church. However, there are no monks or nuns nowadays living there.

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– I don't know

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– No

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Yes

Notes: The Ephorate of Antiquities of Arta of the Greek Ministry of Culture and Sports and Metropolis of Arta of the Church of Greece.

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals who's primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– No

Notes: Yet, the monument still functions as a church.

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– No

Notes: There are monastic cells still preserved next to the church. However, there are no monks or nuns nowadays living there.

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– No

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Yes

Notes: The Ephorate of Antiquities of Arta of the Greek Ministry of Culture and Sports and Metropolis of Arta of the Church of Greece.

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– No

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– I don't know

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– No

Notes: The Refectory of the Monastery is currently used as a museum.

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– No

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– No

Bibliography

General References

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